

**HARMONIC NUMBERS: COMBINATORIAL IDENTITIES AND
SERIES REPRESENTATIONS**

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Abstract

We present several combinatorial identities and infinite series involving the harmonic numbers. Among others, we show that

$$\frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^8} \binom{2n}{n+k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_n^{(2)} - H_{k-1}^{(2)}}{k^2} \sum_{\nu=1}^k \frac{H_\nu^{(2)}}{\nu^2} \quad (n \geq 1)$$

and

$$\frac{H_n}{n} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-1)^j \mu^{j+1} \binom{\nu}{j} \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1} \quad (n \geq 1, 0 < \mu < 2).$$

Here, $H_n = \sum_{k=1}^n 1/k$ and $H_n^{(2)} = \sum_{k=1}^n 1/k^2$ denote the harmonic numbers of order 1 and 2.

1. Introduction and Statement of the Results

I. The classical harmonic numbers are defined by

$$H_0 = 0, \quad H_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}),$$

and the generalized harmonic numbers of order $r \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ are given by

$$H_0^{(r)} = 0, \quad H_n^{(r)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k^r} \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}).$$

H_n can be expressed in terms of the digamma function, $\psi = \Gamma'/\Gamma$,

$$H_n = \psi(n + 1) + \gamma,$$

where γ denotes Euler's constant. Moreover, we have the elegant integral representation

$$H_n = -n \int_0^1 t^{n-1} \log(1 - t) dt, \tag{1.1}$$

see Furdui [7].

The harmonic numbers have interesting applications in various fields, like, for example, number theory, analysis and combinatorics. Lagarias [10] discovered a remarkable connection between H_n and the famous Riemann hypothesis. He proved that the Riemann hypothesis is equivalent to the elementary inequality

$$\sigma(n) \leq H_n + e^{H_n} \log(H_n) \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}),$$

where $\sigma(n)$ denotes the sum of the divisors of n .

The properties of the harmonic numbers have been studied by numerous authors. Hassani [8] discovered the following limit relation for Apéry's constant $\zeta(3)$,

$$\zeta(3) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(H_n^3 - 3 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_{k-1} H_k}{k} \right). \tag{1.2}$$

The reciprocity formula

$$H_{n-1} + \log(n) + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \psi\left(\frac{m+k}{n}\right) = H_{m-1} + \log(m) + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \psi\left(\frac{n+k}{m}\right) \quad (m, n \in \mathbb{N})$$

was given by Ramanujan [5, p. 185]. In the literature, we can find many interesting identities for sums and infinite series involving harmonic numbers. Here are a few examples:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^n \binom{n}{k}^2 \binom{n+k}{k}^2 (1 + 2kH_{n+k} + 2kH_{n-k} - 4kH_k) &= 0, \\ \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k}^2 H_k H_{n-k} &= \binom{2n}{n} ((H_{2n} - 2H_n)^2 + H_n^{(2)} - H_{2n}^{(2)}), \\ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{H_k}{\binom{k+5}{5}^2} &= \frac{75}{4} \zeta(3) - \frac{1075}{8} \zeta(2) + \frac{57175}{288}, \\ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} (H_k^3 - 3H_k H_k^{(2)} + 2H_k^{(3)}) &= 6. \end{aligned}$$

These identities are due to Ahlgren and Ono [1], Batir et al. [4], Sofo [11], Choi [6].

II. In 2015, Kórus [9] applied an identity given by Retkes to present the following combinatorial identities.

Proposition 1. *For all integers $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k} \binom{n}{k} = H_n, \tag{1.3}$$

$$\frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^2} \binom{2n}{n+k} = H_n^{(2)}, \tag{1.4}$$

$$3(n!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^3} \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} = H_n^{(3)}. \tag{1.5}$$

One aim of this paper is to generalize these results.

Theorem 1. *For all integers $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^m} \binom{n}{k} = \sum_{k_{m-1}=1}^n \frac{1}{k_{m-1}} \sum_{k_{m-2}=1}^{k_{m-1}} \frac{1}{k_{m-2}} \cdots \frac{1}{k_2} \sum_{k_1=1}^{k_2} \frac{1}{k_1} \sum_{k_0=1}^{k_1} \frac{1}{k_0}. \tag{1.6}$$

Theorem 2. *For all integers $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{2m}} \binom{2n}{n+k} \\ &= \sum_{k_{m-1}=1}^n \frac{1}{k_{m-1}^2} \sum_{k_{m-2}=1}^{k_{m-1}} \frac{1}{k_{m-2}^2} \cdots \frac{1}{k_2^2} \sum_{k_1=1}^{k_2} \frac{1}{k_1^2} \sum_{k_0=1}^{k_1} \frac{1}{k_0^2}. \end{aligned} \tag{1.7}$$

Theorem 3. *For all integers $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} & 3(n!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{3m}} \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} \\ &= \sum_{k_{m-1}=1}^n \frac{1}{k_{m-1}^3} \sum_{k_{m-2}=1}^{k_{m-1}} \frac{1}{k_{m-2}^3} \cdots \frac{1}{k_2^3} \sum_{k_1=1}^{k_2} \frac{1}{k_1^3} \sum_{k_0=1}^{k_1} \frac{1}{k_0^3}. \end{aligned} \tag{1.8}$$

From Theorems 1–3 with $m = 2, 3, 4$, we obtain the following identities.

Corollary 1. *For all integers $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^2} \binom{n}{k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k}, \tag{1.9}$$

$$\frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^4} \binom{2n}{n+k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k^{(2)}}{k^2}, \tag{1.10}$$

$$3(n!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^6} \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k^{(3)}}{k^3}, \tag{1.11}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^3} \binom{n}{k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k(H_n - H_{k-1})}{k}, \tag{1.12}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^4} \binom{n}{k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_n - H_{k-1}}{k} \sum_{\nu=1}^k \frac{H_\nu}{\nu}, \tag{1.13}$$

$$\frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^6} \binom{2n}{n+k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k^{(2)}(H_n^{(2)} - H_{k-1}^{(2)})}{k^2}, \tag{1.14}$$

$$\frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^8} \binom{2n}{n+k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_n^{(2)} - H_{k-1}^{(2)}}{k^2} \sum_{\nu=1}^k \frac{H_\nu^{(2)}}{\nu^2}. \tag{1.15}$$

$$3(n!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^9} \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k^{(3)}(H_n^{(3)} - H_{k-1}^{(3)})}{k^3}, \tag{1.16}$$

$$3(n!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{12}} \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_n^{(3)} - H_{k-1}^{(3)}}{k^3} \sum_{\nu=1}^k \frac{H_\nu^{(3)}}{\nu^3}. \tag{1.17}$$

Remark 1. Using (1.3), (1.9) and (1.12) gives

$$H_n^3 - 3 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_{k-1}H_k}{k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k} \binom{n}{k} \left(H_n^2 - \frac{3H_n}{k} + \frac{3}{k^2} \right),$$

so that (1.2) leads to

$$\zeta(3) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k} \binom{n}{k} \left(H_n^2 - \frac{3H_n}{k} + \frac{3}{k^2} \right).$$

III. The second aim is to provide one-parameter series representations for H_n/n , the unweighted arithmetic mean of the first n unit fractions, and for the sum $H_1 + H_2/2 + \dots + H_n/n$.

Theorem 4. For all integers $n \geq 1$ and real numbers $\lambda < 1/2$ and $\mu \in (0, 2)$, we have

$$\frac{H_n}{n} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-\lambda)^{\nu+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-\lambda)^{\nu-j} \binom{\nu}{j} S(n, j) \tag{1.18}$$

with

$$S(n, j) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{(k + j + 1)^2} \binom{n}{k}$$

and

$$\frac{H_n}{n} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-1)^j \mu^{j+1} \binom{\nu}{j} \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1}. \tag{1.19}$$

Theorem 5. For all integers $n \geq 1$ and real numbers $\lambda < 1/2$ and $\mu \in (0, 2)$, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-\lambda)^{\nu+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-\lambda)^{\nu-j} \binom{\nu}{j} \left(\frac{H_{j+1}}{j+1} - \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1} \right) \tag{1.20}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-\mu)^{j+1} \binom{\nu}{j} T(n, j) \tag{1.21}$$

with

$$T(n, j) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{(k + j + 1)^2} \binom{n}{k}.$$

We highlight two special cases. Setting $\mu = 1$ in (1.19) and $\lambda = -1$ in (1.20), we obtain the following identities.

Corollary 2. For all integers $n \geq 1$, we have

$$\frac{H_n}{n} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-1)^j \binom{\nu}{j} \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\nu+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} \left(\frac{H_{j+1}}{j+1} - \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1} \right).$$

2. Proofs

We apply a clever variant of the classical proof by induction to establish Theorems 1–3. This method was introduced by Turán [12] to prove an inequality for a sine polynomial with binomial coefficients.

Method. We want to show that $D_{m,n} = 0$ for all integers $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 1$.

Step 1. We prove that $D_{m,1} = 0$ for $m \geq 2$ and that $D_{1,n} = 0$ for $n \geq 1$.

Step 2. Let $m \geq 2, n \geq 1$. We prove that if $D_{m,n} = 0$ and $D_{m-1,n+1} = 0$, then $D_{m,n+1} = 0$.

From Step 1 and Step 2 we conclude that $D_{m,n} = 0$ for $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 1$.

Proof of Theorem 1. We call $L_{m,n}^{(1)}$ the left-hand side of (1.6) and $R_{m,n}^{(1)}$ the right-hand side of (1.6).

Step 1. We have $L_{m,1}^{(1)} = R_{m,1}^{(1)} = 1$ for $m \geq 2$, and from (1.3) we obtain $L_{1,n}^{(1)} = R_{1,n}^{(1)}$ for $n \geq 1$.

Step 2. Let $m \geq 2, n \geq 1$ and $L_{m,n}^{(1)} = R_{m,n}^{(1)}, L_{m-1,n+1}^{(1)} = R_{m-1,n+1}^{(1)}$. Then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} L_{m,n+1}^{(1)} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^m} \binom{n+1}{k} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^m} \left[\binom{n}{k} + \binom{n}{k-1} \right] \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^m} \binom{n}{k} + \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^m} \binom{n}{k-1} \\ &= L_{m,n}^{(1)} + \frac{1}{n+1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{m-1}} \binom{n+1}{k} + \frac{(-1)^n}{(n+1)^{m-1}} \right] \\ &= L_{m,n}^{(1)} + \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{m-1}} \binom{n+1}{k} \\ &= L_{m,n}^{(1)} + \frac{1}{n+1} L_{m-1,n+1}^{(1)} \\ &= R_{m,n}^{(1)} + \frac{1}{n+1} R_{m-1,n+1}^{(1)} \\ &= R_{m,n+1}^{(1)}. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $L_{m,n}^{(2)}$ and $R_{m,n}^{(2)}$ be the expressions on the left-hand side and on the right-hand side of (1.7), respectively.

Step 1. We have $L_{m,1}^{(2)} = R_{m,1}^{(2)} = 1$ for $m \geq 2$, and using (1.4) gives $L_{1,n}^{(2)} = R_{1,n}^{(2)}$ for $n \geq 1$.

Step 2. Let $m \geq 2, n \geq 1$. We assume that $L_{m,n}^{(2)} = R_{m,n}^{(2)}, L_{m-1,n+1}^{(2)} = R_{m-1,n+1}^{(2)}$. Applying the identity

$$\frac{\binom{2n+2}{n+1+k}}{\binom{2n+2}{n+1}} = \frac{\binom{2n}{n+k}}{\binom{2n}{n}} + \left(\frac{k}{n+1} \right)^2 \frac{\binom{2n+2}{n+1+k}}{\binom{2n+2}{n+1}} \quad (1 \leq k \leq n+1)$$

yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{m,n+1}^{(2)} &= \frac{2}{\binom{2n+2}{n+1}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{2m}} \binom{2n+2}{n+1+k} + \frac{2(-1)^n}{(n+1)^{2m} \binom{2n+2}{n+1}} \\
 &= \frac{2}{\binom{2n}{n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{2m}} \binom{2n}{n+k} + \frac{2}{(n+1)^2 \binom{2n+2}{n+1}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{2m-2}} \binom{2n+2}{n+1+k} \\
 &\quad + \frac{2(-1)^n}{(n+1)^{2m} \binom{2n+2}{n+1}} \\
 &= L_{m,n}^{(2)} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^2} L_{m-1,n+1}^{(2)} \\
 &= R_{m,n}^{(2)} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^2} R_{m-1,n+1}^{(2)} \\
 &= R_{m,n+1}^{(2)}. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Theorem 3. We denote by $L_{m,n}^{(3)}$ and $R_{m,n}^{(3)}$ the left-hand side and the right-hand side of (1.8), respectively.

Step 1. We have $L_{m,1}^{(3)} = R_{m,1}^{(3)} = 1$ for $m \geq 1$. Using (1.5) gives $L_{1,n}^{(3)} = R_{1,n}^{(3)}$ for $n \geq 1$.

Step 2. Let $m \geq 2$, $n \geq 1$ and $L_{m,n}^{(3)} = R_{m,n}^{(3)}$, $L_{m-1,n+1}^{(3)} = R_{m-1,n+1}^{(3)}$. We apply the identity

$$\frac{(n+1)^2 \binom{n+1}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^{n+1} (k^2 + kj + j^2)} = \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} + \frac{k^3 \binom{n+1}{k}}{(n+1) \prod_{j=1}^{n+1} (k^2 + kj + j^2)}$$

for $1 \leq k \leq n+1$, and obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{m,n+1}^{(3)} &= 3((n+1)!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{3m}} \frac{\binom{n+1}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^{n+1} (k^2 + kj + j^2)} \\
 &= 3(n!)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{3m}} \frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^n (k^2 + kj + j^2)} \\
 &\quad + \frac{3(n!)^2}{n+1} \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^{3m-3}} \frac{\binom{n+1}{k}}{\prod_{j=1}^{n+1} (k^2 + kj + j^2)} \\
 &= L_{m,n}^{(3)} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^3} L_{m-1,n+1}^{(3)} \\
 &= R_{m,n}^{(3)} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^3} R_{m-1,n+1}^{(3)} \\
 &= R_{m,n+1}^{(3)}. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Corollary 1. The validity of (1.9)–(1.11) is obvious. We only prove (1.12) and (1.13). The proofs of (1.14)–(1.17) are similar. Applying (1.6) with $m = 3$ and the summation formula

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\nu=1}^k A(k, \nu) = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\nu=k}^n A(\nu, k) \tag{2.1}$$

gives

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^3} \binom{n}{k} &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \sum_{\nu=1}^k \frac{H_\nu}{\nu} = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\nu=k}^n \frac{H_k}{\nu k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k} \sum_{\nu=k}^n \frac{1}{\nu} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k(H_n - H_{k-1})}{k}. \end{aligned}$$

Next, we use (1.6) with $m = 4$ and (2.1). This leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k^4} \binom{n}{k} &= \sum_{k_3=1}^n \frac{1}{k_3} \sum_{k_2=1}^{k_3} \frac{1}{k_2} \sum_{k_1=1}^{k_2} \frac{H_{k_1}}{k_1} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\nu=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{\nu} \frac{H_j}{k\nu j} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\nu=k}^n \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{H_j}{k\nu j} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \sum_{\nu=k}^n \frac{1}{\nu} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{H_j}{j} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_n - H_{k-1}}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{H_j}{j}. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

To prove Theorems 4 and 5 we apply a method which has been used in other papers to deduce series representations for certain special functions and for mathematical constants, like, for example, γ , π and Catalan’s constant G ; see Alzer and Koumandos [2], Alzer and Richards [3].

Proof of Theorem 4. (i) Let $0 < x < 1$ and $\lambda < 1/2$. Then $-1 < (x - \lambda)/(1 - \lambda) < 1$. It follows that

$$\frac{1}{1-x} = \frac{1}{1-\lambda} \cdot \frac{1}{1-(x-\lambda)/(1-\lambda)} = \frac{1}{1-\lambda} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-\lambda}{1-\lambda}\right)^\nu. \tag{2.2}$$

From (1.1) and (2.2) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{H_n}{n} &= - \int_0^1 \frac{(1-x)^n \log(x)}{1-x} dx \\ &= - \int_0^1 \frac{1}{1-\lambda} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-\lambda}{1-\lambda}\right)^\nu (1-x)^n \log(x) dx \\ &= \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-\lambda)^{\nu+1}} U(\nu, n) \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} U(\nu, n) &= - \int_0^1 (x-\lambda)^\nu (1-x)^n \log(x) dx \\ &= - \int_0^1 \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} (-\lambda)^{\nu-j} x^j (1-x)^n \log(x) dx \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} (-\lambda)^{\nu-j} S(n, j), \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} S(n, j) &= - \int_0^1 x^j (1-x)^n \log(x) dx \\ &= - \int_0^1 x^j \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-x)^k \log(x) dx \\ &= - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \int_0^1 x^{j+k} \log(x) dx. \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

Since

$$\int_0^1 x^m \log(x) dx = -\frac{1}{(m+1)^2} \quad (0 \leq m \in \mathbb{Z}), \tag{2.6}$$

we obtain

$$S(n, j) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{(k+j+1)^2} \binom{n}{k}. \tag{2.7}$$

From (2.3), (2.4) and (2.7) we conclude that (1.18) holds.

(ii) Let $0 < t < 1$ and $0 < \mu < 2$. Since $-1 < 1 - \mu t < 1$, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{t} = \frac{\mu}{1 - (1 - \mu t)} = \mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} (1 - \mu t)^\nu. \tag{2.8}$$

It follows from (1.1) and (2.6) that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{H_n}{n} &= - \int_0^1 \frac{t^n \log(1-t)}{t} dt \\
 &= - \int_0^1 t^n \log(1-t) \mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} (1-\mu t)^\nu \\
 &= -\mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \int_0^1 t^n \log(1-t) \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} (-\mu t)^j dt \\
 &= -\mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-\mu)^j \binom{\nu}{j} \int_0^1 t^{n+j} \log(1-t) dt \\
 &= \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} (-1)^j \mu^{j+1} \binom{\nu}{j} \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag*{$\square$}$$

Proof of Theorem 5. (i) Using (1.1) and (2.2) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k} &= - \int_0^1 \log(1-t) \sum_{k=1}^n t^{k-1} dt \\
 &= - \int_0^1 \frac{\log(1-t)(1-t^n)}{1-t} dt \\
 &= - \int_0^1 \log(1-t) \frac{1-t^n}{1-\lambda} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{t-\lambda}{1-\lambda}\right)^\nu dt \\
 &= - \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-\lambda)^{\nu+1}} \int_0^1 \log(1-t)(1-t^n)(t-\lambda)^\nu dt \\
 &= \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-\lambda)^{\nu+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} (-\lambda)^{\nu-j} \left(\int_0^1 t^{n+j} \log(1-t) dt - \int_0^1 t^j \log(1-t) dt \right) \\
 &= \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-\lambda)^{\nu+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} (-\lambda)^{\nu-j} \left(\frac{H_{j+1}}{j+1} - \frac{H_{n+j+1}}{n+j+1} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

(ii) We apply (1.1) and (2.8). Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{H_k}{k} &= - \int_0^1 \frac{(1-t^n) \log(1-t)}{1-t} dt \\
 &= - \int_0^1 \frac{(1-(1-x)^n) \log(x)}{x} dx \\
 &= - \int_0^1 \log(x) (1-(1-x)^n) \mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} (1-\mu x)^\nu dx \\
 &= -\mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \int_0^1 \log(x) (1-(1-x)^n) (1-\mu x)^\nu dx \\
 &= -\mu \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu} \binom{\nu}{j} (-\mu)^j T(n, j)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

with

$$T(n, j) = \int_0^1 \log(x) (1-(1-x)^n) x^j dx.$$

Using (2.5), (2.6) and (2.7) gives

$$T(n, j) = S(n, j) - \frac{1}{(j+1)^2} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{(k+j+1)^2} \binom{n}{k}. \tag{2.10}$$

From (2.9) and (2.10) we conclude that (1.21) holds. □

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